

Emeraldine base conducting polymer coatings for protection of steels against corrosion

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Abstract : Open circuit potential (OCP) and potentiodynamic polarization studies were conducted to study the corrosion behavior of emeraldine base coating on AISI 1018 steel in water, sea water, 5% NaCl and 0.1 M HCl.

OCP studies in different media indicate a positive shift in the E_{corr} of coated steel which is maintained for a long time. A positive shift in E_{corr} indicates protective action of the polymer coating. Electrochemical potentiodynamic polarization studies for coated and uncoated steel in HCl show lower corrosion rates for emeraldine base coated steel, an authentic evidence regarding the protection offered by emeraldine base coating in HCl.

Keywords : Corrosion, steel, emeraldine base.

The corrosion of metal can be reduced by using three approaches namely, cathodic protection, passivation (anodic protection) and barrier coating. The protection of metal through anodic passivation can be stated as one of the most significant advances in corrosion science. Application of ionic or conducting polymer such as polyaniline, protects iron or aluminum against corrosion by forming a passivating oxide layer.

Mengoli *et al.*¹ were the first to exploit conducting polymers in the inhibition of corrosion of iron. They deposited the so-called sulfur bridged polyaniline on iron surface by dipping an iron strip in an alkaline water methanol solution of aniline mixed with an inhibitor, allylamine or potassium chromate and ammonium sulfide. Studies carried out by De Berry² confirmed that stainless steel, in the presence of polyaniline was passivated considerably under highly acidic conditions. Passivation occurred even in the damaged areas of the coating. De Berry used the polymer polyaniline in the inhibition of corrosion of SS 410 and 430. The electroactive polyaniline coatings were obtained on the metals of interest by electrochemical treatment in 1.0 M aniline and pH 1.0 perchloric acid solution. Beck *et al.*³ studied the anodic deposition of polypyrrole on iron and other metals. They found that a very strong, adherent, smooth polypyrrole film is deposited if the monomer solution contains oxalic

acid.

Ahmad and MacDiarmid⁴ reported the inhibition of corrosion of iron and steels (pure iron, SS 1018, SS 304, SS 410, SS 430) while studying conducting polymers. Polyaniline was found to be the best polymer because of its environmental stability, easy solution processibility and proper open circuit potential (OCP) in acidic media. The passivation region for SS 430 in 2 N H₂SO₄ was -0.2 to +1.0 V versus saturated calomel electrode (SCE). The minimum potential (-0.2 V vs SCE) needed for passivation of SS 430 is also exhibited by voltammogram of SS 430 in 2 N H₂SO₄, where passivation peak minimum occurs at -0.27 V (SCE). They concluded that the determination of minimum potential required for passivation of iron in a given corrosive medium would be crucial for the selection of a conducting polymer for the corrosion protection of the sample. The V_{OCP} of the conducting polymer chosen for corrosion prevention should be a little higher than the minimum passivation potential of the sample of iron.

The corrosion behavior⁵ of polyaniline-coated steel panels in 3% NaCl solution was studied by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and electrochemical noise method (ENM). EIS data for the polyaniline sample were obtained for increasing time of immersion. An increase in charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) with immersion time

was observed. ENM data showed that active electrochemical changes occurred during early stages of immersion. Tafel plots showed a lower corrosion rate and a more noble corrosion potential for the polyaniline coated sample as compared to a bare steel sample. EIS of polyaniline epoxy two-coated system in steel was also carried out. Performance of the polyaniline epoxy system was superior to that of steel coated with epoxy alone. Similar studies were carried out with various aluminum alloys immersed in dilute Harrison solution (0.35% ammonium sulfate and 0.05% sodium chloride). Polarization experiments and open circuit potential measurements revealed an ennobling of aluminum alloys to higher potential in presence of polyaniline coatings⁶.

The mechanism of protection of steel by conducting polymers appears to involve a redox reaction, perhaps catalytic, to form passivating metal oxide layers at the metal/polymer interface. Conducting polymers exhibited the ability to maintain stable passivity of iron or steel by an oxidising process coupled with O₂ reduction on the surface of metal. Stabilization of the oxide layer by the conducting polymer may play a role in reducing the rate of corrosion. The oxidizing power of polyaniline, rather than its conductivity, appears to play an important role in corrosion inhibition of steel.

Emeraldine, a form of polyaniline, was able to protect steel from corrosion in 0.1 M H₂SO₄ + 0.1 M Na₂SO₄ and also in 0.2 M H₂SO₄ + 0.2 M NaCl, if the problem of adhesion is controlled since the film of polymer separated from the metal⁷. It was found, however, that if the steel is dipped in a solution of phosphoric acid or chelating agent like chromotropic acid or alizarin a good adhesion of polymer is obtained and corrosion was inhibited for longer period (> 30 days) of time. Santos and others⁸ studied the corrosion inhibition and reported loss of water when polyaniline film on metal was kept out of solution. However, it returned to its original form after coming in contact with solution again without losing its electrical and mechanical properties. The protective action of the polymer promotes a change in the corrosion potential to more positive value for carbon steel (~ 100 mV) and for SS (~ 270 mV).

Hettiarachchi *et al.*⁹ published their findings on the use of polyporphyrins and polyphthalocyanins in corrosion inhibition. Polyphthalocyanins were preferred over polyporphyrins because the former had flat structure and could cover steel better than the latter and would retain their electrical conductivity while inhibiting corrosion. The best polymer in this class for corrosion inhibition in

acid environment was the water insoluble tetra-aminophthalocyanin. Ren and Barkey¹⁰ studied the inhibition behavior of polymethylthiophene. They first anodized steel in conc. phosphoric acid, then deposited poly(3-methylthiophene) using a solution of 1.0 M 3-methylthiophene and 0.1 M tetrabutyl ammonium tetrafluoroborate in propylene carbonate at room temperature in air. The black film produced was found to hold the substrate near +0.4 V which is the passive range for SS 430 in 0.5 M H₂SO₄. Sathiyarayanan and Balakrishnan¹¹ while studying inhibition of corrosion of iron in acid solutions found that polyethoxyaniline, a somewhat soluble polymer is better than polyaniline as a corrosion inhibitor. The same investigators established the potential application of harmonic current analysis for corrosion rate measurements. Spink *et al.*¹² carried out a comparative study on the performance of polyaniline (PANI) coatings (both emeraldine salt [ES] and emeraldine base [EB] forms) with epoxy [EP] coatings for corrosion protection of plain carbon steel in a saline solution. While the EB and ES coatings produced higher dissolution rates compared with EP coating, the behavior of coatings was clearly different and short periods of reduced corrosion rates were evident from both ES and EB coatings. The difference in corrosion rates caused by the different forms of polyamide may be associated to different inherent pH. EB produces a highly alkaline environment that is conducive to passive oxide formation while ES produces a mildly acidic environment in which the formation of passive oxide layers is less likely. The performance of new polyaniline (PANI) formulation doped with phosphoric acid was studied¹³. Salt fog exposure tests showed phosphoric acid salts of PANI being more effective for corrosion protection than traditionally used sulfonic acid salts. Scanning reference electrode technology (SERT) data supported the salt fog results. A qualitative model was proposed which entailed passivation of metal surface through anodization of the metal by PANI and formation of an insoluble iron dopant salt at the metal surface.

PANI coatings were electrosynthesised on steel samples using sulfonic and phosphoric acids as supporting electrolytes¹⁴. The protective properties of the coatings were investigated by monitoring the open circuit potential (OCP) and by applying electrochemical impedance spectroscopy. PANI layers were found to provide corrosion protection. Thick PANI layers at 530 mV exhibited pure capacitive behavior at low frequencies in addition to small resistance at higher frequencies. Thin layers at 530 mV exhibited a much higher resistance. The layers deposited in phosphate solution appeared to have better properties

than the layers deposited in a sulfate solution. Tan and Blackwood¹⁵ studied multilayered coatings, consisting of combinations of conducting polymers PANI and polypyrrole (PPY) which were galvanostatically deposited on both carbon steel (CS) and stainless steel (SS). Potentiodynamic polarization was used to assess the ability of these polymers to provide an effective barrier to corrosion in chloride environments. The performance of these multilayered coatings on CS was not sufficiently better than that of single PANI coatings. However, in case of SS, the multilayered coatings proved to be significantly better than single PANI coatings especially at protecting against pitting corrosion. It was found that the degree of protection was a function of the deposition order of the copolymer, with films consisting of a PANI layer on the top of a PPY layer yielding the best results.

The present investigation was undertaken to study the corrosion behavior of emeraldine base coating on carbon steel in different medium. The tests carried out during investigations include free corrosion potential measurements and electrochemical polarization measurements.

Results and discussion

Open Circuit Potential (OCP) measurements :

Figs. 1 to 4 show E_{corr} vs time plots for uncoated and coated steel in different media. Considering the OCP behavior of emeraldine base coating on carbon steel immersed in distilled water, the E_{corr} vs time plot for coated steel (Fig. 1) shows an initial potential of 0.0 mV. The potential remains constant for a couple of days, this

Fig. 1. E_{corr} vs time plot for coated and uncoated carbon steel immersed in distilled water.

is followed by a steep increase in negative potential till it reaches a steady state at about -500 mV after about 7 days. This is followed by a regime of constant potential with occasional shifting to a lower negative potential for the rest of 30 days run. The potential of coated steel is much below the potential of uncoated steel throughout the experiment. The OCP behavior of emeraldine base coating on carbon steel in filtered raw seawater was also studied. The potential of bare steel in filtered raw seawater is about -800 mV. For coated steel, starting with a potential of -190 mV, the negative potential gradually increases up to about -400 mV after 6 days, it remains constant for about 4 days then gradually decreases up to the end of 16 days run (Fig. 2). It appears that the curve is approaching a steady state at a potential of about -250 mV. The

Fig. 2. E_{corr} vs time plot for coated and uncoated carbon steel immersed in filtered raw seawater.

behavior of emeraldine coating in 5% NaCl was also studied (Fig. 3). The initial corrosion potential is about 0 mV which remains constant for about 2 days followed by a steep increase in negative potential, a potential of -575 mV is reached after 3 days and it remained 6+ constant during 16 days duration of the run indicating the attainment of the steady state.

Fig. 4 shows E_{corr} vs time plots for carbon steel (one side coated with nail polish) and emeraldine base coated steel immersed in 0.1 M HCl. For uncoated steel, the initial potential is about -500 mV which goes up to about -570 mV within 10 min. A near steady state representing a constant potential of about -600 mV is achieved within 2 days which continued up to the end of 20 days run.

Fig. 3. E_{corr} vs time plot for coated carbon steel immersed in 5% NaCl solution.

Fig. 4. E_{corr} vs time plot for coated (in two concentration) and uncoated carbon steel immersed in 0.1 M HCl.

For emeraldine base coated carbon steel which was applied in two different concentrations, starting with a low negative potential, the potential is shifted to more negative potential with time and then again shifted to more positive potential. This alternative decrease and increase in negative potential is continued till a near steady state is reached at about -400 mV when there is little change in potential. In general, the time taken to achieve this steady state is found to be increased with increasing thickness or weight of coating. Comparing with control sample without coating in HCl, the potential when the steady state is attained is about -600 mV, this clearly

indicates that the emeraldine base coating in HCl shows a shift to noble potential.

The OCP results on emeraldine base coating on steel immersed in distilled water, seawater, 5% NaCl and 0.1 M HCl show similar pattern in the behavior of coating. Initially the corrosion potential drops to a low negative potential value around 0 mV which sustains for a day or two, exhibiting a passive behavior. This is followed by an increase in negative potential indicating active corrosion at around 400 mV. A few more cycles of decreasing and increasing potentials are invariably observed followed by the attainment of a steady state which is indicated by a constant potential for rest of the run. The decrease and increase in the negative potential for emeraldine base coating in different media is indicative of the attainment of passivity, breakdown or disruption of passivity and repassivation of the coating, respectively. The emeraldine base coating provides protection to steel in different media which is evident from the attainment of constant potential which is considerably lower than the potential achieved by the bare steel in that particular medium.

Electrochemical polarization measurements :

Polarization resistance results :

The results of polarization resistance measurements carried out on uncoated and coated steels in 0.1 M HCl are summarized in Table 1. The uncoated steel shows high corrosion rate on first day. There is a decrease in corrosion rates for a couple of days followed by a further increase in rate. The corrosion rate for coated steel is low which further decreases with increasing exposure time indicating the protective property of emeraldine base.

In another experiment polarization resistance measurements were conducted on two samples having different amounts of coating. After completion of polarization resistance measurements, one sample was subjected to potentiodynamic measurement. In potentiodynamic experiments, the sample was polarized to a higher potential to observe the behavior of coating. Tafel plot was also obtained for emeraldine base coated steel sample. The results are shown in Figs. 5 and 6 and Table 2.

The electrochemical parameters derived from polarization studies indicate very low corrosion rates for emeraldine base coated steel for a considerable period of

Table 1. Polarization resistance measurement of uncoated carbon steel and steel pretreated with hydroxyquinoline sulfonic acid (HQS) and coated with emeraldine base in 0.1 M HCl

Type of steel surface	Period of immersion	Results			
		$E (I=O)$ (mV)	Polarization resistance (K-ohms cm^2)	I_{corr} ($\mu A/cm^2$)	Corrosion rate (mpy)
Uncoated steel (one face and edges covered with nail polish)	Day 1	-546.21	0.2819	77.01	35.3
	Day 2	-559.39	0.6083	35.69	16.36
	Day 3	-590.44	0.6078	35.72	16.37
	Day 6	-601.79	0.3667	59.2	27.13
Coated steel treated with HQS and coated with emeraldine base (back and edges covered with nail polish)	Day 1	-444	-	-	-
	Day 2	-596.24	1.399	15.52	7.11
	Day 3	-594.48	6.76	3.21	1.47
	Day 6	-645.13	4.472	4.85	2.23

Fig. 5. Potentiodynamic polarization curve for coated steel immersed in 0.1 M HCl for 30 days.

Fig. 6. Tafel curve for coated steel immersed in 0.1 M HCl for 30 days.

time. This may be considered as a conclusive evidence regarding the protection offered by emeraldine base coating in HCl. The potentiodynamic and Tafel curves also show some degree of passivity offered by emeraldine base coating.

Conclusions :

- (i) The OCP results on emeraldine coating immersed in distilled water, seawater, 5% NaCl and 0.1 M HCl show similarity in the corrosion behavior of

Table 2. Electrochemical parameters for different concentration of emeraldine base coating on steel as determined from polarization resistance and potentiodynamic studies

Technique	Weight of polymer coating (mg/cm ²)	Medium of immersion	Period of immersion	$E (I=O)$ (mV)	Polarization resistance (K-ohms/cm ²)	Results		I_{corr} ($\mu A/cm^2$)	Corrosion rate (mpy)
						Cathodic Tafel (mV)	Anodic Tafel (mV)		
Polarization resistance	2.11	0.1 M HCl	2 days	-652	284.88	-	-	0.08	0.035
Polarization resistance	1.99	"	30 days	-548.9	57	-	-	0.38	0.177
Potentiodynamic studies	"	"	"	-542.9	-	384.1	257.7	0.72	0.335
Tafel	2.54	"	"	-459.8	-	171.7	449.2	3.48	1.59

coating. The OCP, potential vs time plots show invariably cycles of decreasing (positive shift) and increasing (negative shift) potential followed by a constant potential for the rest of run.

- (ii) The decrease, increase and decrease in the negative potential for emeraldine base coated steel in different media is indicative of the attainment of passivity, breakdown or disruption of passivity and repassivation of the coating, respectively.
- (iii) The emeraldine base coating provides protection to steel in different media which is evident from the attainment of constant potential having a value much lower than the negative potential achieved by the steel in that particular medium.
- (iv) The electrochemical parameters derived from potentiodynamic polarization studies indicate lower corrosion rates for emeraldine base coated steel which is a conclusive evidence for the protection given to steel by emeraldine base coating in HCl.

Experimental

Preparation of specimen :

Sheets of carbon steel AISI 1018 of composition : 0.25% C, 0.52% Cr, 0.51% Ni, 0.30% Cu and 0.62% Si were obtained commercially. Steel specimens of dimensions 25 × 20 × 5 mm were cut from the sheet and were abraded sequentially with 180 and 340 grit SiC papers and finally finished with 600 SiC paper followed by cleaning with acetone. The specimens were weighed and used for the application of coating.

Preparation of the conducting polymer coating :

A saturated solution of 8-hydroxyquinoline sulfonic acid (HQSA) was prepared in distilled water and filtered. Preweighed steel specimen was dipped in HQSA solution for 5 min. The specimen was taken out, dried in air for a short period and was placed in an oven maintained at 100 °C. Saturated solution of emeraldine base in tetramethyl urea (TMU) was prepared and applied on the HQSA treated steel specimen with the help of a dropper. More solution of emeraldine base was placed on the strip in order to get a thick coating. The total volume of the solution added was 1 mL. The specimen was allowed to dry in the oven. The dried specimen was allowed to cool down to room temperature and then its sides and back were covered with clear nail polish. After the air drying of nail polish the specimen was ready for corrosion studies. Before application of nail polish, the amount of polymer coating per cm² of steel was determined.

Free corrosion potential measurements :

The free corrosion potential, E_{corr} of bare and coated steel specimens were measured in 0.1 M HCl, distilled water (pH 6.5), filtered raw seawater (pH 8.5) and 5% NaCl solutions. The steel specimen was connected to a wire having alligator clips on both the ends, one end of the clip was attached to steel specimen and placed into the solution whereas the other end was connected to a multimeter. The change in voltage, against SCE, used as reference electrode, was plotted vs time. The potential measurement in a particular solution was continued till it went down to the potential of bare steel in that medium or attained a steady state.

Electrochemical polarization measurements :

The electrochemical polarization studies were carried out on an EG&G model 342-2 soft Corr measurements system. The system consisted of model 273 potentiostat/galvanostat, model 342 Corr software and model 30 IBM P-2. All the experiments were carried out using a corrosion cell with saturated calomel and graphite as reference and counter electrodes, respectively. Before starting electrochemical measurements, the specimens were left to attain a steady state which was indicated by a constant potential. The polarization resistance measurements were conducted on the same specimen at a scan rate of 0.16 mV/s with starting and final potentials corresponding to -15 mV to +15 mV vs OCP, respectively. Potentiodynamic polarization measurements were performed using a scan rate of 0.2 mV/s commencing at a potential above 250 mV more active than stable OCP.

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